

An Enhanced Fast–High Utility Itemset Mining Method for Large Transactional Datasets

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Abstract

Association mining is widely described for enumerating frequent item sets for deriving corresponding association rules. Sometimes, only the frequency is not a significant concern in the market analysis. Evaluation of support and confidence are recommended to determine for rule strength in terms of user interested items. Profit or utility analysis is also required for improving the market strategies. High Utility Itemset mining is considered one of the critical and challenging problems in data mining. The existing mining framework is facing the problem to analyzing frequency of the items of the database. This framework applies a unique value minimum_utility that fails to finding the different items properties. Recent methods of association mining focused on finding the high utility itemsets instead of frequent itemsets generations. Some utility-based mining methods that is Faster High Utility Itemset Mining (FHM), High Utility Itemset Miner (HUI-Miner), Direct Discovery of High Utility Patterns (D2HUP), Utility Pattern Growth (UP Growth & UP Growth+) are studied for the generation of high utility itemsets generations. Existing HUI mining methods are effectively generating HUIs. However, developing a faster and memory-efficient HUI mining method is required. For this purpose, this work develops an enhanced fast - high utility itemset mining (EF-HUIM) method for the faster generation of HUIs and respective rules.

Keywords:

Association Mining, High Utility Itemset, HUI Mining Methods, Association Rules, Utility Patterns

1. INTRODUCTION

For creating the frequent itemsets, Association Rule Mining (ARM) algorithms [1] are typically utilised. It uncovers intriguing connections and interconnections between massive amounts of data. Dataset analysis benefits from the association rule. The metrics, support and confidence, assess the relationships among tens of thousands of pieces of data. Support provides information on how frequently a given itemset appears in all transactions. Given that the cart already has the antecedents, confidence describes how likely it is that a subsequent event will also occur on the cart. The Apriori [2], Eclat [3], and FP-Growth Algorithm [4] are three types of association rule learning algorithms. Apriori and FP-growth generate association rules using a support and confidence architecture. The things are not prioritised during this process. The objects are therefore seen as having equal importance. Frequently occurring product sets and pertinent association rules are mined using these methods. The apriori algorithm utilises databases with transactional data. To determine frequent item sets, breadth-first search and hash trees are used. It is mostly utilised in market basket analysis and

is straightforward to comprehend and apply. To locate frequent itemsets, the Equivalence Class Transformation (ECLat) algorithm employs a depth-first search strategy. It executes more quickly than the Apriori algorithm. The FP-growth algorithm, which stands for Frequent Pattern and is an enhanced version of the Apriori Algorithm, is related to this. When the Database is large, it becomes difficult to construct and expensive. It displays the Database as a tree structure. Additionally, these are used in continuous production[7], web usage mining[6], market basket analysis[5], etc. We can determine which goods are sold together with the use of ARM approaches, and the main objective of these techniques is to extract all the common itemsets.

Data mining's High Utility Itemset (HUI) [8] mining challenge is regarded as one of its most important and difficult ones. The current mining framework is only capable of examining the database's item occurrence counts. Here, the issue gives a decision-maker more freedom to sift datasets for intriguing and useful patterns utilising item utilities like earnings and margins. One of the core issues with data mining is high utility itemset (HUI) mining. A high utility itemset (HUI) is an itemset whose utility value exceeds a utility threshold that the user specifies. It might be viewed as a more universal form of the frequent itemset. An HUI-based framework for itemset mining gives a decision-maker more freedom to include their own ideas about item utilities like margins and earnings, among other things. The standard frequent itemset mining framework is restricted to examining the Database's item occurrence counts. The main goal of the HUI mining techniques is to extract high utility itemsets (HUIs). Currently used HUI mining techniques successfully produce HUIs. However, it is necessary to create a faster and memory-effective HUI mining method. The Enhanced Fast - High Utility Itemset Mining (EF-HUIM) approach is presented in this study to achieve this goal of producing high utility itemsets more quickly and effectively. In comparison to other algorithms, it uses up to eight times less RAM.

2. BACKGROUND STUDY

Key strategy is to analyze the frequency of the items for the database and it is the only thing that the conventional frequent itemset mining framework [16], [17] is capable of. Instead of focusing on frequent itemset discovery, recent approaches of association mining concentrated on discovering the HUIs. For the generation of HUIs, the utility-based mining techniques, FHM [9], HUI-Miner [10], D2HUP [11], and UP Growth & UP Growth+ [12] are investigated. HUIs are found using the UP-Growth [13] (Utility Pattern Growth) method. In line with this, the essential data of the transaction database pertaining to the utility patterns are defined in a small tree structure known as the UP-Tree [14]. By scanning the database, HUIs from the UP-Tree are produced. It takes a long time for the utility pattern growth technique to generate candidates since it iteratively analyses all conditional prefix trees with a more compressed utility pattern tree.

A better variant of UP-Growth is called UP-Growth+. The number of candidates is decreased together the projected utilities to probable HUIs. By excluding the items utility values are not possibly have a extreme utility or which irrelevant to defined space, the estimated utilities of candidates are effectively decreased. It still requires a lot of time and has a significant computational cost, though.

An approach called Direct Discovery of High Utility Pattern (D2HUP) finds HUIs without keeping track of candidates. It searches the entire database in a single pass to identify the sets of items with the highest utility patterns, but it uses more memory. The utility-list

structure used by High Utility Itemset Miner (HUI-Miner) stores both utility data about the required space during search the space for required items discovery. Utility of other part and vertical data structures are first introduced by HUI-Miner. Comparing UP-Growth and UP-Growth+ to HUI-Miner, fewer candidates are produced.

The enhanced HUI-Miner algorithm is known as Fast High Utility Miner (FHM). It uses utility values of the list for assessing the depth-first search algorithm. In order to decrease the derived count to joint ops during extracting extreme itemset utility values utilising utility_list format, it incorporates a revolutionary approach known as “estimated_utility_co-occurrence_Pruning (EUCP) [15]. The HUI-Miner algorithm is up to more slower compared to FHM algorithm. However, it performs poorly on dense datasets and uses a little bit more RAM than HUI-Miner.

3. PROPOSED EF-HUIM METHOD

According to the associated association rules, the Enhanced Fast - High Utility Itemset Mining (EF-HUIM) method generates high utility itemsets more quickly.

- The Enhanced Fast - High Utility Itemset Mining (EF-HUIM) algorithm's whole architecture is built on the idea that all operations should be carried out linearly in time and space for each itemset found in the search space.
- High-utility Database Projection (HDP) and High-utility Transaction Merging are two effective methods added to the Enhanced Fast - High Utility Itemset Mining (EF-HUIM) algorithm to lower the cost of Database scanning (HTM). These methods use linear time and space implementation to do database projections and merge identical transactions in each projected. As more important itemsets are investigated, both strategies shrink the size of the database, which lowers the cost of database scans.
- To effectively trim the search space, the EF-HUIM method now has two new upper constraints on the utility of the itemsets it uses: Revised sub-tree utility and Local utility. These upper-bounds prune the search space more effectively than the TWU and residual utility upper-bounds, which are frequently employed in older algorithms.
- To determine these upper-bounds in linear time and space, the enhanced Fast - High Utility Itemset Mining (EF-HUIM) algorithm also includes a brand-new array-based utility counting technique called Fast Utility Counting (FAC).

Example Problem

Table 1: A transaction database

TID	Transaction
T10	(p1, “1”) (r1, “1”) (s1, “1”)
T20	(p1, “2”) (r1, “6”) (t1, “2”) (v1, “5”)
T30	(p1, “1”) (q1, “2”) (r1, “1”) (s1, “6”) (t1, “1”) (u1, “5”)
T40	(q1, “4”) (r1, “3”) (s1, “3”) (t1, “1”)
T50	(q1, “2:”) (r1, “2”) (t1, “1”) (v1, “2”)

Table 2: External utility values

Item	p1	q1	r1	s1	t1	u1	v1
Profit	“5”	“2”	“1”	“2”	“3”	“1”	“1”

Table 3: High-Utility itemsets for minutil = 30

Itemset	Utility
{q, s}	30
{p, r, t}	31
{q, r, s}	34
{q, r, t}	31
{q, s, t}	36
{q, r, s, t}	40
{p, q, r, s, t, u}	30

Local Utility and Sub-tree Utility

This EF-HUIM algorithm introduces two new upper restrictions on the utility of itemsets: the updated sub-tree utility and the local utility. Similar higher constraints exist for remaining utility and TWU. The main difference is that these suggested higher boundaries are defined with respect to the sub-tree of an itemset in the search-enumeration tree. The following local utility and sub utility values are explained using the sample data from Tables 1 to Table 3.

3.3.1 Local Utility

Assume an itemset α_1 and an item $z_1 \in E(\alpha_1)$. The Local Utility of z_1 w.r.t. α_1 is

$$Lu_1(\alpha_1, z_1) = \sum_{T \in \text{eg}(\alpha_1 \cup \{z_1\})} [u(\alpha_1, T_1) + re(\alpha_1, T_1)].$$

3.3.2 Sub-Tree Utility

The Sub-tree Utility of z_1 w.r.t. α_1 is

$$Su_1(\alpha_1, z_1) = \sum_{T \in \text{eg}(\alpha_1 \cup \{z_1\})} [u_1(\alpha_1, T_1) + u_1(z_1, T_1) + \sum_{i_1 \in T_1 \wedge i_1 \in E_1(\alpha_1 \cup \{z_1\})} u_1(i_1, T_1)].$$

Algorithm 1: The EF-HUIM algorithm

Input: mutil: It is a user-specified threshold, D is a given database in transactions format.

Output: Discovery of HUIs

1. Set $\alpha_1 = \phi$;
2. To every item, compute $lu_1(\alpha_1, i_1)$ $i_1 \in I_S$ in the database D with assessing the utility_bin ;
3. $Second_1(\alpha_1) = \{i_1 | i_1 \in I_S \wedge lu_1(\alpha_1, i_1) \geq mutil\}$;
4. Assume Υ defined according to TWU increased ordered values on $Second_1(\alpha_1)$;
5. D is scanned for discarding the item $i_1 \notin Second_1(\alpha_1)$ over the database items, items should be sorted to every labelled database D to the Υ , and empty itemsets transactions are to be deleted.

6. According to Y_T sort transactions in D;
7. Compute the utility value of sub tree $subu(\alpha_1, i_1)$ for every I , and $I \in Second_1(\alpha_1)$ during visiting of D using based on array of $utility_bin$.
8. $P(\alpha_1) = \{i | i_1 \in Second_1(\alpha_1) \wedge subu(\alpha_1, i_1) \geq mutil\}$;
9. $Next_S(\alpha_1, D, P(\alpha_1), Second_1(\alpha_1), mutil)$;

Algorithm 1 accepts as inputs of D and a $min_threshold$. The algorithm first views present itemset as an null set in line 1 of the algorithm. The method reads the database once to determine each item's local utility using the $utility_bin$ array in step 2 of the algorithm. The TWU is an item's local utility in the event. The local utility i_1 is then compared with $mutil$ to determine the secondary items; therefore it will be thought of as extensions of (line 3). The products are then arranged in increasing TWU order, and that order will serve as the order (line 4). All items that are not secondary items with respect to are removed from the database since they cannot be included in high-utility itemsets (line 5).

Additionally, each transaction's items are arranged in accordance with. A transaction will be deleted from the database if it is empty. The database is then once again examined in order to arrange transactions according to the T order to enable $O(nw)$ transaction merging (line 6).

When the Search technique, the present itemset to be expanded, the primary and secondary items relative to, the $minutil$ threshold, and the projected Database are all taken into consideration. Each single-item extension of of the form of I is taken into account by the Search algorithm iteratively in a loop, where I is a principal item with respect to I. For each such extension, the database is scanned in order to determine the utility of and simultaneously build the projected database. During the creation of the planned Database, transaction merging is carried out. If the utility of is greater than the $minutil$, then B is the output as a high-utility itemset. The database is then examined once more using two utility-bin arrays to determine the sub-tree and local utility w.r.t. each item z that could expand w.r.t. (secondary items w.r.t). (line 5). It assists in identifying the primary and secondary components. The depth-first search is then extended by executing the Search method.

Illustrative Example

Table 4 shows updated database after performing the various transactions by the customers. these transformations are shown in Table 4. With this database, the transactions are ordered in the form : $T3 < T2 < T4 < T5 < T1$. After this ordering utility of the sub tree is computed with α_1 and the values are $subu(\alpha_1, "p1")=65$, $subu(\alpha_1, "q1")=56$, $subu(\alpha_1, "r1")=54$, $subu(\alpha_1, "s1")=25$, $subu(\alpha_1, "t1")=27$, $subu(\alpha_1, "u1")=5$ and $subu(\alpha_1, "v1")=7$. Therefore, the set $P(\alpha_1) = \{q1, p1, r1\}$ i.e., the depth-first Search will explore only sub-trees of q, p, and r. However, u, v, s, q, p, t, r may be considered in descendant nodes in each sub-tree as they are in $Second_1(\alpha_1)$.

Table 4: Transactional Database shown the items ordered by Y

ID of the Transactions	Item_set_transactions
T3	(u1, "5") (q1, "2") (s1, "6") (p1, "1") (t1, "1") (r1, "1")
T2	(v1, "5") (p1, "2") (t1, "2") (r1, "6")
T4	(q1, "4") (s1, "3") (t1, "1") (r1, "3")

T5	(v1, "2") (q1, "2") (t1, "1") (r1, "2")
T1	(s1, "1") (p1, "1") (r1, "1")

Table 5: Obtained Projected Transactional Database while applying merging

ID of the Transactions	Item_set_transactions
T3	(t1, "1") (r1, "1")
T2	(t1, "2") (r1, "6")
T1	(r1, "1")

The search procedure is called at last to tree according to traversal of depth-first-search then as per the procedure two sets P(alpha1) and Second1(alpha1) are computed.

4. EXPERIMENTAL STUDY

Java was used to implement the algorithms, and the comparison analysis includes memory usage statistics. A collection of benchmarked datasets (Accident, Chess, Foodmart, and Mushroom) were used in the experiments [19], [20]. These datasets were chosen because of their assortment of qualities. Tables 1 and 2 list their traits in detail. The datasets' specifics are as follows: 1) There are a lot of long transactions in the accident's enormous dataset. 2) With its lengthy transactions and few pieces, chess is a rich dataset. 3) Foodmart is a dataset with sparse and brief transactions. 4) With a dense dataset and average-length transactions, mushroom 5) A consumer transaction database called Foodmart has real external and internal utility values. Tables 6 and 7, respectively, offer dataset descriptions and datatypes.

Table 6: Dataset Description

Dataset	#Transactions	#Distinct items	Avg. trans. length
Foodmart	4,141	1,559	4.4
Mushroom	8,124	119	23.0
Chess	3,196	75	37.0
Accident	340,183	468	33.8

Table 7 :Dataset Types

Dataset	Type
Foodmart	sparse, short transactions
Mushroom	dense, moderately long transactions
Chess	dense, long transactions
Accident	moderately dense, moderately long transactions

The following algorithms are used to find the high utility itemsets from the large datasets like Accident, Chess, Foodmart, and Mushroom: UP-Growth, UP-Growth+, D2HUP, HUI-Miner, FHM, and EF-HUIM

The time and space taken by these algorithms and analyzed for determining the HUIs on the same datasets. Firstly, when we consider the time taken by these algorithms to determine the HUIs from the datasets, i.e., Foodmart, Mushroom, Chess, and Accident. The following results are obtained.

Fig 7: Computation Time Comparison

We can observe that the time is taken by the EF-HUIM algorithm for extracting the HUI is less compared to the remaining five

Algorithms.

The following results are obtained when we consider the space taken by these algorithms for extraction of HUIs from the datasets, i.e., Foodmart, Mushroom, Chess, and Accident.

Fig 8: Memory Consumption comparison on the datasets mentioned in Table 6

We can observe that the space is taken by the EF-HUIM algorithm for extracting the is less compared to the remaining five algorithms; which existing algorithms are as follows: FHM, HUI-Miner, D2HUP, UP Growth & UP Growth+.

From the above graphs, we can say that the Enhanced Fast - High Utility Itemset Mining (EF-HUIM) algorithm gives impressive results, i.e., it is efficient in terms of time and space. We can observe that the EF-HUIM algorithm generates high utility itemsets in less time and less space compared to the remaining five algorithms.

5. CONCLUSION AND FUTURE SCOPE

Itemsets with high utility-like earnings are found by extracting the HUIs over the large databases. Most emerging pertinent algorithms related to association mining for the massive number of transactions facing the computational complexity and storage complexity problems. The mining performance suffers due to the processing of massive candidates in terms of the same discussed issues. For the lot of transactions and is pricey, the situation could get worse. This study creates an Enhanced Fast - High Utility Itemset Mining (EF-HUIM) approach to accomplish this goal and create high utility itemsets and associated association rules more quickly. For optimizing the search space of the mining, it uses two most important thresholds of utility. Finding the sub-tree utility and subsequent

local utility would take as the two thresholds of item's utility. According to a thorough experimental analysis on numerous datasets. In the future, real-time market scenarios could be created using dynamic HUI models for analysing massive stream data patterns.

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